

MULTI-LEVEL SENSOR FUSION FOR IMPROVED TARGET DISCRIMINATION

Dr. Claire L. McCullough
Senior Member, IEEE
USASSDC (CSSD-TC-SR)
PO Box 1500
Huntsville, AL 35807-3801
mccullough@ssdch-usassdc.army.mil

Dr. Belur V. Dasarathy
Senior Member, IEEE
Dynerics
PO Drawer B
Huntsville, AL 35814-5050
belur.d@dynerics.com

Perry C. Lindberg
Teledyne Brown Engineering
PO Box 070007
Huntsville, AL 35807-7007
perry_lindberg@pobox.tbe.com

ABSTRACT

A project was sponsored by the U.S. Army Space and Strategic Defense Command (USASSDC) to develop, test, and demonstrate sensor fusion techniques for target recognition. The sensor fusion architecture developed for this program exploits the use of sensor fusion at all levels (signal, feature, and decision levels) to improve target recognition capability against Tactical Ballistic Missile (TBM) targets. It was hypothesized that use of fusion at all these levels is necessary to give a system robustness to noise and sensor degradation and to accommodate a wide variety of mission and target types. This would address problems such as ineffective sensors, missing data, and invalid classifier assumptions. Thus, the critical objective of the new fusion system architecture is to permit graceful degradation rather than catastrophic failure whenever some components of the system, whether hardware or software, fail to perform adequately.

Two tests were conducted on the trained discrimination algorithms: a blind test with simulated noisy signatures collected at angles different from those in the training database and a test using actual radar field test data collected during flight of a representative TBM target. The test results demonstrate a high degree of recognition accuracy. The presentation will describe the training and testing techniques used, show the fusion strategy employed, and illustrate the advantages of exploiting multi-level fusion.

INTRODUCTION

Classification algorithms were trained with simulated radar signatures generated with an enhanced version of the RASIG code, with improved diffraction coefficients and fin scattering added. The simulated signatures represent measurements made by S-band and X-band radars with the targets at a variety of aspect and roll angles, ranging from 0 to 45 degrees aspect and 0 to 360 degrees roll. Noise levels in the training data span a range thought to be representative of the genuine test data. Four different types of TBM targets were included in the simulated data base; the real world test data is from an actual flight of one of the four simulated target types. Classifiers were required to identify each target from a "snapshot" of radar data--i.e., a single waveform rather than a

time series of data. This is actually more difficult than the standard discrimination problem, as many of the most widely used features for target discrimination from radar data require a time series of returns.

A single classifier, a supervised neural network, was used to make class decisions at the signal level based on the fused radar signals from X- and S-bands. Three classical feature level classifiers were used: a maximum likelihood classifier, a nearest neighbor classifier, and a piecewise sequential classifier. These three classifiers were used to separately make class decisions based on the fused feature data that was extracted from the two radar signals. The results of these three feature level fusion processes were combined in a simple voting scheme to obtain the first decision level fusion result. Decisions from the two best performing feature level classifiers were then combined, also in a voting scheme, with the results of the neural network, for the second decision level fusion result. The decisions of all three feature level classifiers were combined with the neural net results using simple expert system rules to obtain the results of the final fusion.

RESULTS

The results for the blind test against simulated data are given in Figure 1, below. Representative low, medium, and high noise level results are shown, for the fused X and S band results. Note that each of the classifiers has classification results which degrade as noise levels increase, as one would expect; however, even at high noise levels, recognition accuracy is still good. Although there is no classifier which has superior performance over all target types, some classifiers are superior at recognizing a *particular* target. This information was used in generating decision rules for an expert classifier called the "smart voter." This variation on a simple voting scheme incorporated key rules such as:

- a) If classifiers disagreed, the decision of the classifier with highest probability of success in recognizing the specific target type was followed;

b) If a classifier couldn't make a decision, it wasn't allowed a vote in the combined decision.

Results against the genuine test data were not as impressive as those from the simulated data, partially due to lack of fidelity in the target models: the more sophisticated scatterers and radar enhancers were not modeled, as the budget of the program was limited, and proof of concept of the fusion architecture was the primary goal. A large portion of the error, however, is probably due to the erroneous assumption, made independently by each of the researchers, that since the radars were co-located and were looking from a common angle at a common target, that noise levels of the two would be similar. In fact, the noise level of the X-band radar was between one and two orders of magnitude greater than that in the S-band. Thus, the correct training sets for each classifier should have included X-band data at each noise level paired with S-band data at the same noise level, and at each of the other noise levels. In this particular project, the cost of such training would have been prohibitive, as it would have increased the training set for each classifier by a factor of four. The results using the test data also gave some interesting indications of in what situations fused discrimination is advantageous in the case of two different sensors observing the same phenomenology: when pairing very good data from one sensor with very bad data from another, the effect of fusion is to actually *decrease* classification accuracy; this is intuitively what would be expected. The most improvement from fusion in this experiment seemed to come when outputs of two *moderately* successful classifiers were combined. Cases such as this, where two sensors have significantly differing performance parameters, may be more suitable for decision level fusion, as differing noise levels would have no effect on the results in that case. Two of the classifier types, CDF2 and Expert are not included in the results of the field test data: each of these required post-processing of the decisions of the other classifiers; this was not practical due to the classified nature of the field test data and the stringent restrictions placed on classified processing. Although the results against the actual test data were not as impressive as those using the simulated signatures, the results do show that the algorithmic approach should be effective given the appropriate level of fidelity and noise levels for the training database.

CONCLUSIONS

While more work remains to be done on this project, these preliminary results do clearly demonstrate the efficacy of the proposed methods and architecture, and give indications of when fusion aids discrimination and when it hinders. The planned eventual architecture will be as shown in Figure 2: classifiers at each of the discussed levels, raw data, feature and decision, will be incorporated, but an intelligent controller will provide guidance as to how the decisions will be combined. This controller is envisioned as a more sophisticated version of the expert fusion used here, incorporating such aspects of the problem as mission type, atmospheric conditions, noise level, and sensor performance parameters. Additional planned future work includes extending the concepts here to fusion of radar

with an imaging sensor, and including time series of data to allow exploitation of temporal effects, as well as additional classifier work including training a neural network based on the target features rather than the raw data and fuzzy coding of features. Methods and architectures presented here are also applicable to a variety of additional applications such as fingerprint recognition, ballistic identification, and character recognition problems.

Figure 1. Discrimination Performance Summed Over all Target Types

Figure 2. Complete Proposed Fusion Architecture